

EUROPEAN SOCIETY OF
MYCOBACTERIOLOGY

ABSTRACT BOOK 2025

45TH
ANNUAL
CONGRESS

INSTITUTO DE
HIGIENE E MEDICINA
TROPICAL LISBON

22-25 JUNE 2025

P044

In vitro modelling of the tuberculosis granuloma for antimicrobial and host-directed drug screening

B Fontes¹ R Ferreira¹ M Mandal² R Pinheiro¹ E Anes² PJG Bettencourt¹
S David^{2,3} D Pires^{1,2,3}

1: Center for Interdisciplinary Research in Health, Católica Medical School, Universidade Católica Portuguesa, Portugal 2: Host-Pathogen Interactions Unit, Research Institute for Medicines, iMed.Ulisboa, Faculty of Pharmacy, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal 3: Departamento de Genética Humana, Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA), Lisbon, Portugal

To accelerate the discovery of new antimicrobials or host-directed therapies, we have developed an in vitro 3D cell culture model of the TB granuloma. The model can be easily applied using commercial systems to encapsulate human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) infected with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* H37Rv (Mtb). The 3D granuloma structure exhibited a drastically lower Mtb burden with bacterial growth confined to a restricted number of cells, in contrast to the standard monolayer model. Manipulation of the macrophage and lymphocyte content showed clear distinctions in the ability to control Mtb infection, and introduction of lymphocytes helped control the infection even when the cells were physically separated. Different multiplicities of infection (MOI) didn't affect the ability of Mtb to survive and replicate. Yet, at the lowest MOI, we observed a lower expression of proinflammatory markers and increased expression of anti-inflammatory markers. The model allowed infection assays to last up to one month, with cell viability mainly affected by the bacterial burden. The onset of bacterial replication correlated with increased cell death, primarily in the macrophage population. Some of the granulomas exhibited a distinct region of dead cells at the centre of the structure. The treatment with antibiotics showed greater resistance to isoniazid, followed by rifampicin, and increased susceptibility to pyrazinamide compared to the standard monolayer infection model.

In conclusion, the 3D model resembles some features expected in the TB granuloma, which we will explore in future drug discovery studies.

P045

Phagocytosis of *Mycobacterium fortuitum* by caprine alveolar macrophages is associated with iNOS and proinflammatory marker expression

M Blay-Benach^{1,2} J Repullés^{1,2} P Cuenca-Lara^{1,2} B Pérez de Val^{1,2}

1: Programa de Sanitat Animal, Centre de Recerca en Sanitat Animal (CRESA), IRTA, Campus de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain 2: Unitat Mixta d'Investigació IRTA-UAB en Sanitat Animal, CRESA, Campus UAB, Spain

Phagocytosis mediated by alveolar macrophages (AM) plays a crucial role in host defence against pathogens such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. However, limitations of *in vitro* phagocytosis assays highlight the need for new methods to assess AM functionality. This study aimed to standardize and evaluate a novel fluorescence-based technique for measuring the phagocytosis of *M. fortuitum* by caprine AM and its association with AM activation and proinflammatory markers. AM were stimulated *in vitro* with LPS and heat-inactivated *M. bovis* (HIMB) for 24h. After

stimulation, AM were exposed to fluorescently labelled *M. fortuitum* for 72h and fluorescence kinetics were measured using the Incucyte® SX5 Live-Cell Imaging and Analysis System. This method was compared to a culture-based assay using the MGIT BACTEC system. In addition, AM activation and polarization markers were assessed using flow cytometry, while a multiplex immunoassay was performed to quantify proinflammatory cytokines. The fluorescence intensity kinetics indicated that stimulation with LPS, but not HIMB, resulted in a greater signal reduction compared to unstimulated AM, suggesting a higher bacterial elimination. Similarly, LPS induced a higher percentage of mycobacterial reduction measured by MGIT culture between 2 and 72h after *M. fortuitum* challenge. Moreover, LPS stimulation increased the production of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1b, IL-6, TNFa), elevated the proportion of cells co-expressing iNOS and MHC-II, and enhanced the expression of these markers within M1-polarized AM, suggesting that LPS induced a more activated proinflammatory phenotype. These findings indicate that enhanced mycobacterial phagocytic capacity of AM correlates with iNOS and MHC-II expression and a proinflammatory profile.

P046

Mycobacteria extracellular vesicles as alternative immunotherapy for Bladder cancer

B Yewew^{1 2} R Sorrentino² C Venegoni³ P Miotto² C Braccia⁴ A Andolfo⁴
A Salonia³ M Alfano³ DM Cirillo^{1 2}

1: Vita-Salute San Raffaele University, Milan, Italy 2: EBPU, IRCCS San Raffaele Scientific Institute, Milan, Italy 3: URI, IRCCS San Raffaele Scientific Institute, Milan, Italy 4: Proteomics and Metabolomics Facility (ProMeFa), IRCCS San Raffaele Scientific Institute, Milan, Italy

Bladder cancer (BC) is the 9th most common cancer worldwide. BCG installation remains the standard treatment for high-grade non-muscle-invasive cases, but its limited efficacy and side effects highlight the need for alternatives. Mycobacterial extracellular vesicles (MEVs) have emerged as promising immunomodulatory agents, providing a unique opportunity for immunoncology applications. Therefore, we assessed the antitumor capability of different MEVs against BC cell lines (BCaCL). MEVs were isolated from OncoTICE BCG, *M. tuberculosis* reference strain H37Rv and environmental *M. gordonae* (MG) by ultracentrifugation; quantified and characterized by Nanosight and BCA assay. Dose-response assays were performed on BCaCLs (T24, 5637) and THP-1-derived macrophages. Cell viability (Calcein-AM) was assessed at 24 and 72 h, and cytokine levels (ELISA) at 24 h post-treatment with MEVs or live BCG. T24 proteins were extracted after 72 h of MEVs treatment (BCG or H37Rv-derived), BCG-infection or untreated cells and analyzed by nLC-MS/MS. MEVs induced dose-dependent cytotoxicity in BCaCLs (12–48% viability reduction) and triggered TNF and IL-12 secretion comparable to BCG infection. IL-6 levels increased by 50–100% relative to BCG-infected cultures. However, MEVs significantly impacted macrophage viability (over 40% reduction). Proteomic analysis identified 228 statistically significant differentially expressed proteins ($p < 0.05$) across the four groups. MEVs demonstrated cytotoxicity and cytokine induction in BCaCLs, like BCG infection. Their impact on macrophage activation remains under investigation. Proteomic analysis revealed limited differences between MEV-treated and BCG-infected cells in terms of immunological activation, supporting further exploration of MEVs as modulators of immune responses in bladder cancer.
